

Influence of Attached Rings on the Formation and Stability of Heterocyclic Compounds.

Part II.

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In part I (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 10, 583) a hypothesis has been developed on the basis of some experimental facts that the fused benzene ring helps ring-formation, and the effect appears to increase with the increase in the number of benzene rings. In order to confirm further this idea, the present investigation has been undertaken.

β -Arylthiocarbamidopropionic acid (I) is obtained from β -amido-propionic acid and isothiocyanate. It does not, however, suffer any change even when boiled with strong hydrochloric acid for a long time.

β -Phenyl- β -arylthiocarbamidopropionic acid (II), obtained from β -amido- β -phenylpropionic acid and isothiocyanate, yields, on treatment with acetic anhydride, a thiazine derivative (III) which cannot be desulphurised by oxide of mercury. The thiazine derivative (III) is easily hydrolysed to compound (II) by normal alkali even in the cold.

It has already been found (Ghosh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 981) that anthranilic acid gives a quinazoline derivative with isothiocyanate, instead of *o*-arylthiocarbamidobenzoic acid and that this quinazoline is converted into a benzothiazine derivative by the action

of strong sulphuric acid. The above benzothiazine derivative cannot be hydrolysed even by 10 % alcoholic potash or strong acids.

The dipotassium salt of *o*-benzoyleneurea, obtained by the action of hot alcoholic potash, gives the corresponding diethyl derivative (IV) (Bogert and May, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, 31, 512) showing that alkali cannot bring about the hydrolysis of *o*-benzoyleneurea.

β -Lactylurea, on the other hand, is decomposed, on being similarly treated with alkali, into the potassium salt of β -aminopropionic acid.

o-Phenylcarbamidobenzoic acid (Paal, *Ber.*, 1894, 27, 978) yields, on treatment with acetic anhydride, a benzoxazine derivative (V).

Similarly β -phenyl- β -phenylcarbamidopropionic acid (VI), obtained from β -amido- β -phenylpropionic acid and phenyl isocyanate, yields with acetic anhydride an oxazine derivative (VII).

Both of the above compounds (V and VII) are slowly hydrolysed to the corresponding acids in decinormal alkali at ordinary temperature but at higher temperature the conversion is too rapid to allow any comparative study of the velocity coefficient.

Salicylidene-anthranilic acid (VIII) yields with acetic anhydride a lactone (IX) which remains unchanged in presence of cold normal alkali. This remarkable stability of the eight membered lactone ring (IX) is evidently due to the presence of the two fused benzene rings.

Now the very fact that straight chain compounds (I and II) are always obtained from β -amidopropionic acid or its substitution products with thiocarbimides, whereas under exactly similar conditions, quinazolines are obtained from anthranilic acid and thiocarbimides and that benzothiazine and *o*-benzoyleneurea are much more stable than the thiazine derivative (III) and β -lactylurea respectively, shows conclusively how the fused benzene ring helps ring-formation and stabilises the heterocyclic systems.

From the recent velocity coefficient measurements of Guha-Sircar (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 600, 1253) it is found that the coefficient for the hydrolysis of homophthalimide is nearly half of that of glutarimide, which, in the light of the observations now made, can be explained as being due to the presence of the fused benzene ring in homophthalimide. Further, there are many heterocyclic compounds known the formation of which can be explained on the basis of the hypothesis developed in this paper. It is well known that in *ortho*-substituted phenols *e.g.*, *o*-hydroxybenzoic acids, their esters and aldehydes, *o*-nitrophenols, the polar character due to the hydroxylic hydrogen is absent in much the same way as if this hydrogen were replaced by methyl. Philip (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1903, 83, 820) has found that *o*-nitrophenol does not condense with aniline as the *m*- and *p*-isomerides do. On the basis of electronic theory of valency, Sidgwick and Callow (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 128, 532) have explained the peculiar behaviour of the *ortho*-substituted phenols of the above type on the assumption that the hydroxylic hydrogen participates in a chelate ring-formation which can only happen if the

hydrogen forms a co-ordinate link with some atom of the second substituent thus :

These six membered rings belong to the most stable type of chelate ring known. It is further known that the hydroxyl group which behaves in a peculiar manner when attached to the benzene ring, retains its normal and characteristic property when attached to a straight chain system, showing firstly, that there is no formation of chelate ring in the latter and secondly, that the formation of the chelate ring is evidently due to the presence of the fused benzene ring.

In order to explain this behaviour of the fused benzene ring in helping ring-formation and promoting ring-stability of heterocyclic systems, reference may be made to a very interesting paper of Mills and Nixon (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 2510) who have shown by mathematical calculations of the angles of the carbon atoms that round the benzene ring adjacent valencies will be closer when the carbon atoms are joined by a single bond. In the open-chain series there being no such influence, the ring-formation does not take place so readily.

Some further interesting examples of the stability of analogous heterocyclic systems have been observed in cases where a double bond exists just outside the heterocyclic ring. When glycine reacts with isothiocyanates (*cf.* Aschan, *Ber.*, 1884, 17, 420) in each case a mixture of the corresponding diazole derivative (X) which is soluble in alkali and a small quantity of diarylthiourea has been obtained. The diazole is easily hydrolysed by equimolecular quantity of alcoholic alkalis yielding arylthiocarbamidoacetic acid

(XI). The diazole contains a reactive methylene group and readily reacts with aldehydes to give the compound (XII) which,

however, is remarkably resistant even towards 10% alcoholic alkalis.

This stability is evidently due to the double bond which has been introduced in compound (XII).

It is interesting to note that the compound (XII) is not desulphurised by oxide of mercury, whereas the original diazole (X) is easily desulphurised, showing firstly that the compound (XII) exists only in the tautomeric form and secondly, that the reactivity of the

methylene group is conditioned by the presence of the grouping $-\text{CO}-\overset{\overset{|}{\text{N}}}{\text{C}}-$ and has been increased by duplication within a ring (*cf.* Higginbotham and Lapworth, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 2826). This observation is confirmed by the fact that neither arylthiocarbamidoacetic acid nor phenylhydantoin reacts with aldehydes under usual conditions.

The compound (XIII), obtained from the diazole (X) and *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde, yields a quinoline derivative (XIV) on reduction with tin and hydrochloric acid (*cf.* Baeyer and Drewson, *Ber.*, 1883, 16, 2207).

The stability of compounds of the type (XII) compares favourably with that of the fused benzene-heterocyclic systems described in the

preliminary portion. Although it is not possible at this stage to offer any explanation for this similarity of behaviour in the two types of compounds, it may be just likely that the stability of the compounds of the type (XII) is conditioned by similar steric considerations as offered by Mills and Nixon (*loc. cit.*).

EXPERIMENTAL.

β-*o*-Tolylthiocarbamidopropionic acid (I, R=*o*-tolyl).—*β*-Aminopropionic acid (2.2 g.), prepared according to the method of Hoogewerff and Dorp (*Rec. Trav. Chim.*, 1891, 10, 4) was dissolved in water to which an alcoholic solution of *o*-tolyl isothiocyanate (3.7 g.) was added and the solution was boiled under reflux for about an hour and cooled when a solid came out which crystallised from dilute alcohol in colourless prisms, m.p. 144-45° (decomp.). (Found: N, 11.49. C₁₁H₁₄O₂N₂S requires N, 11.76 per cent). It is soluble in sodium bicarbonate solution and does not suffer any change even when boiled with strong hydrochloric acid for a long time. It is desulphurised to an alkali insoluble compound (m.p. 236-37°) which could not be further studied due to poor yield.

β-*p*-Tolylthiocarbamidopropionic acid (I, R=*p*-tolyl) was crystallised from dilute alcohol in colourless prisms, m. p. 151-52° (decomp.). (Found: N, 11.52. C₁₁H₁₄O₂N₂S requires N, 11.76 per cent).

β-Phenyl-*β*-phenylthiocarbamidopropionic acid (II, R=phenyl).—An alcoholic solution of *β*-phenylpropionic acid (3.3 g.), prepared according to the method of Posner (*Ber.*, 1905, 38, 2320) and phenyl isothiocyanate (2.7 g.) was heated under reflux for about 2 hours and evaporated when a crystalline mass was obtained which dissolves readily in sodium bicarbonate solution and is precipitated by acids. It is very soluble in alcohol, ether and acetic acid and was crystallised from very dilute acetic acid in colourless prisms, m. p. 145-46° (decomp.). (Found: S, 10.41. C₁₆H₁₆O₂N₂S requires S, 10.66 per cent). It is easily desulphurised by yellow oxide of mercury and does not suffer any change even when boiled with strong hydrochloric acid.

1-Phenylamino-3-keto-5-phenyl-2:6-thiazine (III, R=phenyl).—2 G. of the above compound (II, R=phenyl) were heated with acetic anhydride (30 c.c.) for about an hour when the clear solution,

on cooling, deposited a colourless crystalline mass. A further quantity of the substance was obtained by adding water to the acetic anhydride solution which was being stirred vigorously. It was crystallised from acetic acid in colourless needles, m. p. 232-33° (decomp.), yield 1.2 g. (Found: S, 11.07. $C_{16}H_{14}ON_2S$ requires S, 11.34 per cent). It is not desulphurised by oxide of mercury. When it is kept in contact with normal caustic potash solution for 2-3 hours a clear solution is obtained which, on acidification, yields a colourless precipitate crystallising from dilute acetic acid in prisms, m. p. 145-46° (decomp.). The identity of this compound with the compound (II, R=phenyl) was confirmed by mixed m. p., properties and finally by analysis.

β-Phenyl-β-o-tolythiocarbamidopropionic acid (II, R=*o*-tolyl) was crystallised from dilute acetic acid in colourless prisms, m. p. 154-55° (decomp.). (Found: S, 9.88. $C_{17}H_{18}O_2N_2S$ requires S, 10.19 per cent).

1-o-Tolylamino-3-keto-5-phenyl-2:6-thiazine (III, R=*o*-tolyl) was crystallised from acetic acid in colourless needles, m. p. 169°. (Found: S, 10.53. $C_{17}H_{16}ON_2S$ requires S, 10.81 per cent). It is also easily hydrolysed by caustic potash solution.

Diethyl derivative of o-benzoyleneurea (IV).—*o*-Benzoyleneurea (1 mol.) was dissolved in alcoholic potash (caustic potash, 2 mols.) which was heated under reflux for about an hour and then evaporated almost to dryness. The potassium salt thus obtained is very soluble in cold water from which it is precipitated by the addition of large quantity of alcohol in beautiful colourless plates, m. p. above 300°. On acidification it yielded *o*-benzoyleneurea. It was dissolved in the smallest quantity of water to which an alcoholic solution of ethyl iodide (2 mols.) was added and the solution was boiled under reflux for about half an hour and then evaporated. The product was crystallised from dilute alcohol in beautiful colourless slender needles, m. p. 108°. (Found: N, 12.82. $C_{12}H_{14}O_2N_2$ requires N, 12.84 per cent). Bogert and May (*loc. cit.*) give 105.6° as the m. p. of the compound.

Action of alkali on β-lactylurea.—*β*-Lactylurea (1 mol.) was dissolved in alcoholic potash (caustic potash being 2 mols), heated under reflux for about an hour and evaporated almost to dryness. The potassium salt was dissolved in cold water and acidified when an effervescence of carbon dioxide began. No solid, however, came out. From the clear solution *β*-aminopropionic acid was isolated accord-

ing to the method of Hoogewerff and Dorp (*loc. cit.*) and identified with a genuine sample.

1-Phenylamino-3-keto-4:5-benzo-2:6-oxazine (V).—An acetic anhydride solution of *o*-phenylcarbamidobenzoic acid (5 g.) was heated under reflux for about half an hour. The clear solution, on cooling, gave a mixture of a quinazoline derivative (already prepared by Paal, *loc. cit.*) and the oxazine derivative, from which the latter was separated by treatment with very dilute alkali and crystallised from alcohol in colourless prisms, m. p. 124-25°, yield 1.5 g. (Found: N, 11.48. $C_{14}H_{10}O_2N_2$ requires N, 11.76 per cent).

β -Phenyl- β -phenylcarbamidopropionic acid (VI).— β -Amido- β -phenylpropionic acid (3.3 g.) was dissolved in dilute alcohol to which phenyl isocyanate (2.3 g.) was added. The precipitate was crystallised from alcohol in colourless needles, m. p. 168-69° (decomp.), yield 4.5 g. (Found: N, 9.72. $C_{16}H_{16}O_3N_2$ requires N, 9.85 per cent).

1-Phenylamino-3-keto-5-phenyl-2:6-oxazine (VII).—The method of preparation was the same as in the case of the compound (III). The product was crystallised from alcohol in colourless slender needles, m. p. 221-22°. (Found: N, 10.31. $C_{16}H_{14}O_2N_2$ requires N, 10.52 per cent).

Salicylidene-anthranilic acid (VIII).—An acetic acid solution of anthranilic acid (2.7 g.) and salicylaldehyde (2.4 g.) was heated under reflux for half an hour when a yellow crystalline mass was obtained which further crystallised from acetic acid in yellow needles, m. p. 188-90°, yield 3.5 g. (Found: N, 5.53. $C_{14}H_{11}O_3N$ requires N, 5.81 per cent). It is soluble in aqueous solution of sodium bicarbonate.

Action of acetic anhydride on the above compound (VIII): *Formation of compound* (IX).—The method of procedure was the same as in the case of the compound (III). The product was crystallised from alcohol in colourless prisms, m. p. 156-57°. (Found: N, 6.08. $C_{14}H_9O_2N$ requires N, 6.27 per cent). It is not readily soluble in cold normal alkali but when kept in presence of the cold alkali for a day it goes into solution which, on acidification, yields the original compound (VIII). When it is heated with strong hydrochloric acid, the solution, on cooling, deposits a colourless crystalline mass which has been identified to be anthranilic acid hydrochloride.

1-Keto-4-thioketo-5-p-tolyl-3:5-diazole (X, R = *p*-tolyl).—Glycine (3.8 g.) was dissolved in the smallest quantity of hot water to which

an alcoholic solution of *p*-tolylisothiocyanate (7.5 g.) was added. The solution was boiled under reflux for about an hour and then evaporated to dryness. The crystalline precipitate was treated with cold dilute caustic potash solution when a small portion remained undissolved. The rose-coloured alkaline solution, on acidification, gave a yellowish precipitate which crystallised from alcohol in yellowish needles, which darken at 205° emitting strong smell of mercaptan and melt completely at 229-30°, yield 8 g. (Found: N, 13.41. $C_{10}H_{10}ON_2S$ requires N, 13.59 per cent).

The product insoluble in alkali was crystallised from alcohol in colourless plates, m.p. 176°. The identity of this compound with di-*p*-tolylthiourea was proved by taking a mixed melting point and finally by analysis.

1-*Keto-4-thioketo-5-o-tolyl-3:5-diazole* (X, R=*o*-tolyl) was crystallised from alcohol in yellowish needles, m.p. 145-46°. (Found: N, 13.37. $C_{10}H_{10}ON_2S$ requires N, 13.59 per cent). The alkali-insoluble compound was similarly proved to be di-*o*-tolylthiourea.

p-Tolylthiocarbamidoacetic acid (XI, R=*p*-tolyl).—The above compound (X, R=*p*-tolyl; 3.8 g.) was dissolved in 100 c.c. of alcohol containing 1.3 g. of caustic potash. The rose-coloured clear solution was heated under reflux for about an hour and evaporated to dryness. The solid was washed several times with absolute alcohol and crystallised from water in colourless prisms. It is the potassium salt of *p*-tolylthiocarbamidoacetic acid, colours pink on heating and melts at 240° (decomp.). (Found: N, 10.46. $C_{10}H_{11}O_2N_2SK$ requires N, 10.69 per cent). The *free acid* was obtained as a colourless precipitate when a cold aqueous solution of the above potassium salt was acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid. It crystallised from hot water in colourless rectangular plates, m.p. 147-48° (decomp.). (Found: N, 12.31. $C_{10}H_{12}O_2N_2S$ requires N, 12.50 per cent). It is readily soluble in sodium bicarbonate solution.

o-Tolylthiocarbamidoacetic acid (XI, R=*o*-tolyl) was crystallised from dilute alcohol in colourless prisms, m.p. 141-42° (decomp.). (Found: N, 12.28. $C_{10}H_{12}O_2N_2S$ requires N, 12.50 per cent).

1-*Keto-2-benzal-4-thioketo-5-phenyl-3:5-diazole* (XII, R=R'=phenyl).—A glacial acetic acid solution of benzaldehyde (2.1 g.) and the diazole derivative (X, R=phenyl; 3.8 g.) was heated under reflux for about an hour. The clear solution, on cooling, deposited a crystalline mass which further crystallised from alcohol in beautiful

yellowish plates, m.p. 196-97°. It is soluble in dilute alkali and is precipitated by acids. (Found: N, 10.13. $C_{16}H_{12}ON_2S$ requires N, 10.0 per cent). It is not desulphurised by oxide of mercury and remains unchanged even when heated with 10 % alcoholic potash.

1-Keto-2-benzal-4-thioketo-5-p-tolyl-3:5-diazole was crystallised from alcohol in yellowish plates, m.p. 180-81°. (Found: N, 9.31. $C_{17}H_{14}ON_2S$ requires N, 9.52 per cent).

1-Keto-2-o-nitrobenzal-4-thioketo-5-phenyl-3:5-diazole (XIII, R = phenyl).—The product, obtained by condensing *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde with the diazole derivative (X, R = phenyl) in acetic anhydride solution, was crystallised from alcohol in yellow needles, m.p. 216-18°. (Found: N, 12.64. $C_{16}H_{11}O_3N_3S$ requires N, 12.92 per cent).

Reduction of the above compound (XIII): Formation of compound (XIV, R = phenyl).—The above compound (5 g.) was heated under reflux with strong hydrochloric acid (70 c.c.) and granulated tin (25 g.) for about 3 hours when a clear solution was obtained. The solution was then diluted with water when a precipitate came down which crystallised from dilute alcohol in brownish white needles, m.p. 186°, yield 1.5 g. (Found: N, 14.88. $C_{16}H_{11}N_3S$ requires N, 15.16 per cent). It is soluble in alkali and is precipitated by acids.

Further work in this line is in progress.

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